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Supplementary Information for

**A simple genetic basis of adaptation to a novel thermal environment results
in complex metabolic rewiring in *Drosophila***

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Supplementary Methods
Supplementary Results
Figures S1 to S17
Tables S1, S6, S7

19 **Supplementary Methods**

20

21 ***Drosophila simulans* population sample**

22

23 In summer 2008, we established 250 isofemale lines from a *Drosophila simulans* collection in
24 Northern Portugal (Póvoa de Varzim). After about 10 generations in the laboratory, we
25 generated 10 independent replicate ancestral populations. For each replicate we used five
26 mated females from each of the 250 isofemale lines (1250 females in total). These females
27 were distributed across five bottles containing 70 ml standard *Drosophila* medium.

28

29 **Culture conditions during experimental evolution**

30

31 The flies were propagated in two fluctuating temperature regimes: five replicates evolved in a
32 hot treatment with 12 h at 18°C (dark) and 12 h at 28°C (light), the other five replicates in a
33 cold treatment with 12 h at 10°C (dark) and 12 h at 20°C (light). The populations evolving in
34 the two temperature treatments were processed in the same way, except that the time after
35 which flies were transferred to a new bottle was adjusted to account for the slower
36 development at lower temperatures. Approximately three days after eclosion of a new
37 generation (four to five days in the cold treatment), all flies from the five bottles were
38 combined. After careful mixing the adults within each replicate, five samples of 200
39 individuals each were transferred to fresh bottles. After 48h (72h) of egg-laying in the hot
40 (cold) environment, adults were transferred again to fresh bottles for another 48h (72h), after
41 which flies were either frozen or used for DNA extraction. To prevent selection for early
42 fecundity, flies eclosing from the first transfer were only used if the second transfer did not

43 yield enough flies to maintain a population size of 1000 individuals per replicate (5 bottles
44 with 200 flies).

45

46 **Common garden experiments**

47

48 Prior to phenotypic assays and RNA-Seq, all five replicate populations of the hot and the cold
49 evolved treatment as well as from a reconstituted ancestral population [80] were maintained
50 in a constant 23°C common garden environment for two generations to control for maternal
51 effects.

52 At generation 64 in the hot and generation 39 in the cold environment the common garden
53 experiments were set up from additional egg lays. These eggs were transferred to a constant
54 temperature (23°C, 12:12h light/dark cycles). In parallel, an ancestral population was
55 reconstituted from the isofemale lines as described in Tobler et al. 2015 [26], a procedure,
56 which faithfully mirrors the allele frequencies in the founder populations [80]. During the
57 common garden experiment and phenotyping, this ancestral population was maintained in
58 parallel to the evolved ones. After one generation of acclimatization, groups of 300 eggs were
59 transferred to fresh bottles (i.e.: density control). Shortly after eclosion, adults were collected
60 and sexed under CO₂ anesthesia. Males were separated from females and recovered 24-36h
61 from CO₂ treatment before being frozen in liquid nitrogen at 2pm (approx. 6h after the light
62 cycle started in the incubators).

63

64 **Gene expression analysis**

65

66 The RNA was quality-controlled on agarose gels and quantified using the Qubit RNA HS or
67 BR Assay kit (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA). We generated strand-specific barcoded mRNA

68 libraries using the NEBNext® Ultra Directional RNA Library Prep Kit for Illumina with a
69 protocol modified to allow for a larger insert size than the default 200bp.

70 PolyA-mRNA was purified from 3µg total RNA and fragmented for 8 min. The 42°C
71 incubation step in the first-strand synthesis and the 16°C step in the second-strand synthesis
72 were extended to 30 and 90 min., respectively. Size selection for a target insert size of 330bp
73 was performed using AMPure XP beads (Beckman Coulter, Carlsbad, CA). PCR enrichment
74 was done using NEBNext Multiplex oligos following the recommended protocol with 12
75 PCR cycles and a 50 sec. extension step.

76 The final libraries were bead-purified, quantified with the Qubit DNA HS Assay kit
77 (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) and pooled in equimolar amounts. Samples from ancestral, cold
78 and hot evolved replicates were combined in the same pool, i.e. sequenced in the same lane,
79 to reduce batch effects. Libraries were sequenced using a single-read 50bp protocol on a
80 HiSeq2500.

81 Two of these libraries had a too low coverage to be analyzed (Table S4) and we finally
82 obtained data from 28 libraries (nine ancestral, nine cold and 10 hot evolved).

83

84 **RNA-Seq quality control**

85

86 We performed several analyses to test the quality of each library. First we determined
87 coverage heterogeneity, i.e.: a 3' bias, using the geneBody_coverage tool implemented in the
88 RSeQC package [81]. Since the 3' bias is most pronounced for long genes, we performed this
89 analysis using the 20% longest genes of the *D. simulans* transcriptome (the bed file is
90 available on demand). Strongly biased libraries were removed from all subsequent analyses
91 (see Fig. S4 for an explanation of the cutoff used).

92 Based on 12 chorion and yolk protein genes we tested for female gene expression in male
93 samples to identify female contamination due to sexing mistakes (Table S5). We excluded
94 four outlier libraries that showed total log₂ normalized expression of these genes higher than
95 eight (see Fig. S5). After removing female contaminated libraries and libraries with 3' bias, a
96 total of 20 libraries (five ancestral, seven cold and eight hot evolved libraries) remained for
97 analysis. Spearman correlation coefficients between all libraries showed a correlation of at
98 least 0.948 between libraries. Despite some heterogeneity among libraries, a multi-
99 dimensional scaling plot did not show outliers. Therefore, we retained all 20 remaining
100 samples for differential gene expression analysis.

101

102 **Supplementary Results**

103 Analysis of the peaks of genetic differentiation

104 The top 100 SNPs retained for the analysis were mainly clustered in 4 major peaks of allelic
105 differentiation on chromosome arms 2L, 3L and 3R (see Fig3, Table S3). Further analysis
106 using a clustering approach (restricted to the peaks containing *SNF4Aγ* and *Sestrin*) [38]
107 showed that these peaks likely contain a single selected haplotype block. In addition to the
108 two peaks described in the main text, we identified two additional peaks that must contain a
109 selected variant. The first one encompasses a very large region of the 3L chromosome arm
110 containing more than half of the top 100 SNPs (n=54) over almost 5Mb. It is thus difficult to
111 identify potential targets of selection. Nevertheless, the highest significant SNPs are close to
112 *Fie* that is involved in temperature sensing and none of the genes close to these most
113 significant SNPs of this peak are involved in metabolism regulation. The last peak is located
114 on the chromosome arm 3R and contains 24 of the 100 top SNPs. Most of them map to a
115 single gene (*Ace*, 20 SNPs). This gene is known to be selected in natural populations for

116 insecticide resistance and we have evidence that the selection around this loci in our
117 experiment is not temperature specific as it is also selected in our cold environment
118 (unpublished data). Furthermore, we show that the selection response at *Ace* is driven by the
119 cost of insecticide resistance in an insecticide free environment. Hence, we consider it
120 unlikely that the observed changes at *Ace* are associated with metabolism regulation.

121 **Analysis of low frequency ancestral alleles**

122 In order to ensure that the high repeatability of the allele frequency changes observed across
123 our 5 evolved populations was not due to accidental contamination during our experimental
124 procedure, we looked for low frequency alleles in the ancestral populations increasing during
125 our experiments. If some of the observed consistent signal of allele frequency increase is due
126 to a combination of contamination and drift, then these replicate specific SNPs should be rare
127 and not evenly distributed across the genome.

128 We called the SNPs that at very low frequency the ancestral population (<0.5%) but present at
129 more than 30% frequency in one evolved population and absent in the remaining four evolved
130 populations. Because we detected such SNPs in all replicates distributed along all major
131 chromosome arms (see Table S7), we do not consider migration a strong evolutionary force in
132 our experiments.

133

134 Resting metabolism

135 In a second series of measurements after 133 generations, neither the interaction body
136 weight:population nor body weight alone were non-significant ($P=0.68$ and $P=0.23$
137 respectively). The difference between hot evolved flies and the reconstituted ancestral
138 population was only significant if body weight was included as a fixed effect in our model
139 (see Fig. S3), suggesting that in addition to sex, other factors affected body weight between

140 populations. Since body weight is an important factor influencing CO₂ emission, we included
141 body weight as a random effect in a mixed linear model and found a significant difference
142 between the two populations ($\chi^2_{3,4}=0.98$, P=0.045). Because this value is close to the 5%
143 threshold, we additionally tested for significance using bootstrapping by generating 10,000
144 random data sets having the same distribution as in our null model and computed the test
145 statistic for each of these data sets. The random data sets were created using the function
146 ‘simulate’ from the package stats in R applied to our null model (a mixed linear model with
147 no fixed effect and only containing the random effect). For each simulated data set, we then
148 computed the mixed models with and without population as fixed effect. Finally, we
149 calculated the log-likelihood ratio test statistic comparing these two models for each
150 simulated data set and compared this distribution to the statistic obtained from the true data
151 set. We found that simulated test statistics are higher than the true one only 4.3% of the time,
152 confirming the significant differences between the hot evolved and reconstituted ancestral
153 populations.

154 Computer simulations

155 For several parameter combinations the allele frequency changes (i.e. CMH p-values) did not
156 match our experimental results (red background color). With few background loci (5,10, 25),
157 the focal loci are not increasing sufficiently in frequency because their phenotypic effects are
158 on the same order of magnitude as the background loci. For the remaining parameter
159 combinations (blue), the two focal loci explained between 43 and 97% of the total phenotypic
160 change of the population (see Figure 4). The simulations reliably reproduce our experimental
161 results when the initial distance to the phenotypic optimum is larger than the summed
162 contribution of our two focal loci (>0.3), but also less than twice this contribution. This is
163 because when the ancestral distance to the phenotypic optimum is low enough, most of the
164 phenotypic change is achieved by our two focal loci. Yet, as the ancestral distance to the

165 phenotypic optimum increases, there are more opportunities for low effect size loci to
166 increase in frequency and the probability to detect them is increased.

167 Finally, we made the simplifying assumption that all background loci have the same effect
168 size, which is unrealistic. Although we did not test this, we assumed that in the case of
169 heterogeneous effect sizes of background loci, most of the unexplained phenotypic increase
170 would be associated with the background loci with the strongest effect sizes.

171

172 **References**

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174 isofemale lines as a tool for experimental evolution. *Ecol Evol.* 2016;6:7169–75.
- 175 81. Wang L, Wang S, Li W. RSeQC: quality control of RNA-seq experiments.
176 *Bioinformatics.* 2012;28:2184–5.

177

178

179 **Table S1**

180 List of genes consistently down- or up-regulated in the contrast between the ancestral and the
 181 two evolved populations (laboratory adaptation). The table presents the log₂ fold changes and
 182 p-values for each comparison ancestral-cold evolved and ancestral-hot evolved. Negative log₂
 183 fold changes indicate that the expression is decreased in the evolved populations (and
 184 reciprocally).

FBgn	Symbol	log ₂ FC (Anc/Hot)	P (Anc/Hot)	log ₂ FC (Anc/Cold)	P (Anc/Cold)
FBgn0034612	CG10505	-1.8212	9.20E-18	-1.0091	5.55E-06
FBgn0030332	CG9360	-1.5041	2.14E-17	-1.2137	6.14E-11
FBgn0032381	Mal-B1	-1.0457	6.76E-07	-1.2880	1.41E-08
FBgn0000473	Cyp6a2	-0.9832	2.74E-06	-1.2715	4.36E-08
FBgn0033065	Cyp6w1	-0.9489	1.60E-05	-1.3693	2.54E-08
FBgn0033204	CG2065	-0.9033	1.22E-10	-0.6662	1.38E-05
FBgn0033981	Cyp6a21	-0.7575	3.32E-10	-0.5281	2.95E-05
dsim_PG00121	-	-0.7506	6.14E-09	-0.7896	1.94E-08
FBgn0013772	Cyp6a8	-0.7065	4.76E-04	-0.7981	1.66E-04
FBgn0027600	obst-B	-0.6887	2.52E-08	-0.5110	7.34E-05
FBgn0013773	Cyp6a22	-0.6831	3.23E-05	-0.6628	1.13E-04
FBgn0000008	a	-0.6624	2.51E-08	-0.5290	2.23E-05
FBgn0014469	Cyp4e2	-0.5947	1.56E-06	-0.5199	7.50E-05
FBgn0038734	CG11453	-0.5904	1.85E-07	-0.5497	3.97E-06
FBgn0010053	Jheh1	-0.5764	3.39E-04	-0.6737	5.66E-05
FBgn0038194	Cyp6d5	-0.5691	9.14E-05	-0.5687	2.75E-04
FBgn0038516	P5cr-2	-0.4922	3.57E-05	-0.4878	5.41E-05
FBgn0030615	Cyp4s3	-0.4049	2.10E-05	-0.5020	3.24E-07
FBgn0261800	LanB1	0.2821	3.10E-03	0.3887	5.45E-05
FBgn0037000	ZnT77C	0.3725	5.99E-05	0.4084	1.95E-05
FBgn0259140	CG42255	0.4344	4.29E-04	0.5434	1.36E-05
FBgn0010241	Mdr50	0.4754	7.53E-07	0.3641	3.19E-04
FBgn0263973	juv	0.6652	8.96E-10	0.4187	1.57E-04
FBgn0265267	CG18258	0.7218	4.95E-11	0.4603	3.65E-05
FBgn0262880	CG43235	0.7389	6.85E-05	0.7188	1.86E-04
FBgn0029147	NtR	0.7559	2.62E-04	0.7701	2.45E-04
FBgn0032136	Apoltp	0.7580	2.34E-15	0.4370	9.15E-06
FBgn0041607	AsnS	0.7871	5.40E-06	0.6817	1.38E-04
FBgn0032322	CG16743	1.0781	4.99E-15	0.6308	6.81E-06
dsim_PG00244	-	1.1202	6.42E-05	1.6259	6.71E-09
FBgn0035619	CG10592	1.2504	2.14E-10	0.7589	1.11E-04
FBgn0051324	CG31324	1.4001	7.89E-21	0.6080	1.06E-04
FBgn0035620	CG5150	1.5397	2.30E-15	0.7918	3.42E-05
FBgn0033729	Cpr49Af	1.5669	9.66E-04	1.9010	1.02E-04
FBgn0039471	CG6295	1.7332	8.85E-10	1.2142	2.31E-05

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189 **Table S6.**190 **Description of the extraction and library preparation methods used for each sample**
191 **(genomic data).**

Library	DNA isolation	Amount of starting material	Fragmentation method	Kit	Size selection method	Insert size (bp)	Polymerase	No. of PCR cycles	Sequencing platform	Read length (bp)
Founder females A	DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit ¹ including RNase A treatment	5 µg	Nebulizer	Illumina Paired-End DNA Sample Prep protocol ³	Agarose gel	210	Phusion ⁴	10	GAllx	2 x 74
Founder females A	DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit ¹ including RNase A treatment	5 µg	Nebulizer	Illumina Paired-End DNA Sample Prep protocol ³	Agarose gel	210	Phusion ⁴	10	GAllx	2 x 76
Founder females B	DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit ¹ including RNase A treatment	5 µg	Covaris S2 ²	Illumina Paired-End DNA Sample Prep protocol ³	Agarose gel	340	Phusion ⁴	10	HiSeq 2000	2 x 100
Founder females A & B	DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit ¹ including RNase A treatment	ca. 4 µg	Covaris S2 ²	NEBNext Mastermix Kit E6040L and NEB Multiplex Oligos (single-index) for Illumina ⁴	AMPure XP beads ⁵	380	NEB Q5 ⁴	6	HiSeq 2500	2 x 120
Hot F2	DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit ¹ including RNase A treatment	5 µg	Covaris S2 ²	Illumina ³ Paired-End DNA Sample Prep protocol	Agarose gel	340	Phusion ⁴	10	HiSeq 2000	2 x 100
Hot F59 r1,r3,r5	High salt extraction protocol ⁴³ including RNase A treatment	2 µg	Covaris S2 ²	Reagents of TruSeq Paired-End Sequencing Kit ³ ; ligation of TruSeq single-index adapters followed by pooling of ligated fragments; PCR amplification of the multiplexed size-selected fragments using the TruSeq mastermix ³	Agarose gel	270	TruSeq PCR Mastermix ³	10	HiSeq 2000	2 x 100
Hot F59 r1,r3,r5	High salt extraction protocol including RNase A treatment	1 µg	Covaris S2 ²	Reagents of NEBNext Ultra DNA library preparation kit E7370L ⁴ ; size selection of each individual library on agarose gels; PCR amplification of individual libraries using NEB Multiplex (single-index) primers ⁴ followed by pooling	Agarose gel	310	NEB Q5 ⁴	10	HiSeq 2000	2 x 100
Hot generation 59 replicate 2,4	High salt extraction protocol ⁴³ including RNase A treatment	ca. 4 µg	Covaris S2 ²	NEBNext Mastermix Kit E6040L and NEB Multiplex Oligos (single-index) for Illumina ⁴	AMPure XP beads ⁵	380	NEB Q5 ⁴	6	HiSeq 2500	2 x 120
Haplotypes	High salt extraction protocol ⁴³ including RNase A treatment	ca. 100 ng	Covaris S2 ²	NEBNext Ultra DNA II Library Prep Kit ⁴	AMPure XP beads ⁵	410	NEB Q5 Hot Start ⁴	8	HiSeq 2500	2 x 125

192 1 Qiagen, Hilden, Germany

193 2 Covaris, Inc. Woburn, MA, USA

194 3 Illumina, San Diego, CA

195 4 New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA

196 5 Beckman Coulter, Carlsbad, CA

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Table S7.

Number of replicate specific SNPs detected in each evolved populations on the main chromosome arms.

	X	2L	2R	3L	3R	4
Hot - Rep 1	239	239	151	133	183	131
Hot - Rep 2	83	83	52	50	212	155
Hot - Rep 3	165	179	72	60	305	1
Hot - Rep 4	122	122	100	133	231	113
Hot - Rep 5	107	107	171	143	720	146

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208 **Fig. S1.**

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Barplots showing log₂ fold change of expression between the hot evolved populations relative to the ancestral (green) or cold evolved (blue) populations. (** FDR<0.05, * FDR<0.1). Left panel: Fat metabolism genes. Right panel: Insulin signaling pathway genes.

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215 **Fig. S2.**

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Allele frequency changes during 59 generations of experimental evolution for the 28 SNPs showing a correlated response across 5 hot evolved populations in the *SNF4A γ* region.

220 **Fig. S3.**

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224 CO₂ emission is measured over two subsequent generations at 23°C. Although variable, the
225 two mean emission is statistically different between the two populations when the variation in
226 body weight between samples is accounted for. Closed symbols: mean with 95% confidence
227 interval; open symbols: single measurements (n= 2*16), green: reconstituted base, red:
228 population evolved in the hot environment for 133 generations.

229

230 **Fig. S4.**

231
232 Relative coverage across genes for 28 RNA-Seq libraries. We removed three libraries (in red)
233 from our analysis, because they exhibited a very pronounced 3' bias: at 50% gene body length
234 the relative coverage was below 90%.
235

236

237 **Fig. S5.**

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239 Identification of libraries with female contamination. We summed the expression of the nine

240 chorion genes (CP15 to 19, CP36, CP38) and three yolk proteins (YP1 to 3). We excluded

241 four outlier libraries (in red) with > 256 counts per million bp for the 12 indicator genes.

242

243 **Fig. S6.**

244
245 Estimation of the selection coefficient using the poolSeq R package individually for each of
246 the detected SNPs in the *SNF4A γ* region. Arrows represent 95% confidence intervals. All
247 values are significantly different from zero ($p < 0.01$). Median value = 0.07,
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249 **Fig. S7.**

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A close up of Manhattan plot around the *Sestrin* region. On top of the Manhattan plot the gene structure of *Sestrin* (leftmost blue gene) is shown. Exons are indicated by colored boxes and introns by thin lines. White boxes indicate UTRs. From left to right the genes are: *Sestrin* (blue), CG18128 (yellow), *egl* (green), CG13560 (purple), CG11300 (blue), CG5532 (small purple), CG9850 (long purple). Red triangles indicate 95 correlated SNPs, which characterize the selected haplotype(s).

258 **Fig. S8.**

259

260 Allele frequency changes during 59 generations of experimental evolution for the 95 SNPs
261 showing a correlated response across 5 hot evolved populations in the *Sestrin* region (2R:
262 17520000-17600000).

263

264

265 **Fig. S9.**

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268 Estimation of the selection coefficient using the poolSeq R package individually for each of
269 the detected SNPs in the *Sestrin* region. Arrows represent 95% confidence intervals. All
270 values are significantly different from zero ($p < 0.05$, 69 SNPs have $p < 0.01$). Median value =
271 0.06,

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273

282 **Fig. S11.**
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285
286 Haplotype structure in the *SNF4A γ* region (10kb before and after the selected loci, 1106
287 SNPs, 3R:4,239,687:4,271,358). We detected multiple haplotypes containing all the selected
288 alleles (blue labels), while the remaining ones show low variability. Yellow and green codes
289 for non-selected polymorphism (ancestral and derived alleles respectively); missing values are
290 plotted in gray color.

291 **Fig. S12.**
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294
295 Haplotype structure in the *Sestrin* region restricted to the 95 SNPs showing correlated
296 frequency increase. We detected in both evolved populations (Rep1 and Rep3) some
297 haplotypes carrying either all the selected alleles (in blue). Missing values are plotted in gray
298 and counter-selected alleles in red.
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301 **Fig. S13.**
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304 Haplotype structure in the *Sestrin* region (1444 SNPs, 3L:17,520,080:17,587,103). We
305 detected multiple haplotypes containing all the selected alleles (blue labels), while the
306 remaining ones show low variability. Yellow and green codes for non-selected polymorphism
307 (ancestral and derived alleles respectively); missing values are plotted in gray color.
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309

310 **Fig. S14.**

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312 SNPs characterizing the selected haplotype at the *SNF4A γ* locus in the experimental evolution
313 study show clinal variation in natural populations (Machado et al.). 21 out of 28 SNPs had
314 sufficient coverage in the Machado et al. data set. 11 SNPs displayed clinal variation. The
315 decrease in frequency from Florida to Maine, is consistent with the observation that these
316 alleles are favored in the hot experimental evolution cage.
317

318 **Fig. S15.**

319
320 SNPs characterizing the selected haplotype at the *SNF4A γ* locus in the experimental evolution
321 study show clinal variation in natural populations: Machado et al.⁵ data set. 21 out of the 28
322 SNPs had sufficient coverage in the Machado et al. data set. Left panel: Allele frequencies of
323 the alleles favored in the hot cage in Florida (red) and Maine (blue). Right panel: Distribution
324 of t.statistics obtained from random sampling of 21 SNPs in the region of interest. In more
325 than 99% of the time the true set of SNPs (red vertical line) are more clinal than randomly
326 sampled SNPs.
327

328 **Fig. S16.**

329
330 SNPs characterizing the selected haplotype at the *SNF4Aγ* locus in the experimental evolution
331 study show clinal variation in natural populations: Sedghifar et al.¹⁰ data set. 15 out of the 28
332 SNPs were also detected in the Sedghifar et al data set. Left panel: Alleles favored in the hot
333 cage are found more frequently in the Florida (South) than in the Rhode Island (North, left
334 panel, 15 SNPs). Right panel: Only 32 out of 10,000 of the t.statistics computed by random
335 sampling of 18 SNPs from the 122 SNPs of the region of interest are lower than the one
336 computed from the true set of SNPs. Left panel: Allele frequencies of the *SNF4Aγ* hot alleles
337 found in the Sedghifar et al.¹⁰
338

339 **Fig. S17.**

340
341 Australian populations. Here the clinal pattern is found in the opposite direction, hot alleles
342 are less frequent in the lower latitude population (Queensland, median AF = 0.77) than in the
343 higher latitude one (Tasmania, median AF=0.87, 23 SNPs). Left: Only 26 out of 10,000 of
344 the t.statistics computed by random sampling of 25 SNPs from the 380 SNPs of the region of
345 interest are lower than the one computed from the true set of SNPs.

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